

AUTHENTIC ASSESSMENT TOOL FOR WRITING COMPETENCE: ITS BASES AND DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Writing is an essential macro-skill, and it is imperative for communication and the dissemination of information. In order to improve students' writing skills, authentic assessment is used to provide students with realistic tasks that prepare them for the real world. It is a crucial factor that guarantees students' success in school, the workplace, and real life. To achieve that, this research was dedicated to the design of an English authentic assessment tool to enhance students' writing competence. The study employed a predominantly qualitative research design, which is the generic or basic qualitative inquiry, and was conducted via two processes: analysis and design. Data collection was obtained through a survey of Grade 10 students and five English teachers and a systematic literature review of secondary sources. Analysis of collected data was accomplished using Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis, which generated codes of patterns. When the themes and sub-themes of the primary and secondary sources were outlined, a cross-case analysis was utilized to determine and combine similarities. The features, challenges, and gaps found in the sources were used as the basis for the design of the authentic assessment tool or rubric. A rubric assesses students' outputs from a list of standards, and it is composed of three broad categories that focus on the context, process, and evaluation of authentic writing tasks. The goal of the rubric is to help teachers with an authentic assessment tool to supplement their teaching writing strategies and strengthen their pedagogical practices.

Keywords: *Writing as a macro-skill, authentic assessment, thematic analysis, rubric*

INTRODUCTION

The English language has four macro-skills: listening, reading, speaking, and writing. Each skill is necessary to learn and master to acquire language proficiency. Listening and reading skills are considered inputs in the process of developing language; on the other hand, speaking and writing skills are regarded as outputs. Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines writing as the formation of letters to express words and ideas. Writing renders any language visible, makes thoughts and ideas tangible and permanent, and becomes a representation or record of any human language.

In the hierarchy of macro-skills, researchers debate that writing is the most challenging. It is a productive and effective skill that involves more than arranging expression on paper, and it requires writers to monitor and scrutinize several linguistic and semantic elements, such as grammar, mechanics, organization, content, and language. According to Saavedra and Barredo (2020), a learner is regarded as proficient and competent in a particular language if the learner can compose within the rudimentary rules of the language.

Writing is a fundamental skill that students need to learn and master. According to Hikmah et al. (2019), writing is meant to express ideas, opinions, thoughts, and feelings. Many researchers iterate that writing is critical for students, and acceptable writing skills are required for students to accomplish and succeed in their educational and employment requirements. The following are some of the practical applications of writing skills that are mandated in education and the workplace sectors: writing technical documents and research papers, searching and obtaining a job, making presentation and reports, improving communication skills, and improving creativity, exploration, and self-understanding (Durga & Rao, 2018, p.3).

Unfortunately, there is an alarming case in the students' writing skills. Based on the work of Alostath (2021), there are two reasons for the writing concerns: the teachers are not aware of pedagogical and assessment strategies in teaching writing, and the students possess low-level syntactical knowledge in composing complete and coherent sentences and paragraphs. Second, technology plays a role in diminishing students' drive to master their writing skills because artificial intelligence (AI) tools can produce ready-made texts in a matter of seconds. Third, a lack of motivation and willingness to learn and write also impacts students' writing skills. Writing apprehension can derail students' cognitive writing process because they are worried about internal and external factors. According to Valderama (2019), in the study of Saavedra and Barredo (2020), these explain the declining English proficiency of Filipinos and are supported by the study conducted by the Swiss-based company, English Proficiency First. It was found that Filipinos' English Proficiency Index (EPI) declined to 14th and 20th places in 2018 and 2019, respectively.

In order to alleviate the concerns regarding the weakening writing skills of students, they need to be given support to enhance their writing skills. Due to the increasing need for a practical approach to learning assessment, authentic tasks are developed to copy

real-world challenges and standards. Authentic assessment is defined as making visible and measurable performance, showcasing the specific curriculum competencies integrated into the conditions they are intended to be used or needed (Gulikers et al., 2014, as cited in Mardjuki, 2018). When the students are exposed to writing tasks with real-life applications, they will have a higher chance of academic and professional growth. Schools and universities must strive to provide real-world contexts to students to prepare them for life after graduation.

Despite its favorable influence on student learning, authentic assessment also has drawbacks. Enforcing assessment activities that reflect real-world contexts in the classroom demands time and mastery. Several studies showed challenges in implementing the authentic assessment, such as time limitation of learning and complexity of procedures in preparing authentic assessment techniques and instruments; also, there is a significant concern regarding how authentic tasks should be.

The purpose of this study was to bridge the gap between the implementation of authentic assessment and the improvement of students' writing skills. Due to the challenges experienced by students in improving their writing skills and by teachers in implementing authentic assessment, the researcher aimed to create an authentic assessment tool to guide teachers in planning, implementing, and evaluating authentic writing tasks.

The assessment tool is a response to students' dwindling writing skills, as mentioned in the EPI of Filipinos, which dropped to 14th and 20th places. The poor linguistic performance of the students is supported by the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) 2019 study, which revealed a significant disparity in Filipino pupils' writing competency. It was found that 37.2% of the overall variation in writing achievement scores of the students is accounted for by between-school differences, which is considered substantial for education research.

To sum up, through the continuous and knowledgeable use of an authentic assessment tool, the students will apprehend the pertinence of the writing task to their present and prospective academic and professional endeavors. Thus, they will be more predisposed to enhance their writing skills. Moreover, the study aimed to help teachers with an authentic assessment tool to supplement their teaching writing strategies and strengthen their pedagogical practices. Finally, the study contributed to the current research regarding the efficacy of authentic assessment as a better assessment approach.

Research Objective

This study aimed to design an English authentic assessment tool for enhancing writing competence.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a predominantly qualitative research design, which is the generic or basic qualitative inquiry. According to Merriam and Tisdell (2016), generic research endeavors to comprehend further the phenomenon and how the study correlates to it. It focuses on the understanding of the meaning people construct of their experiences, and it addresses the “why” and “how” behind human behavior. Finally, this exercise uses an inductive approach, which begins with a general understanding of the phenomenon. The data collection and analysis were accomplished to gather information to develop a more specific understanding of the phenomenon (Liamputtong, 2019).

The methodology of the study outlines the specific techniques and procedures used to identify, select, process, and analyze information about a topic (University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, 2025). The collected data were obtained from two sources of information: a survey and a systematic literature review.

The primary source of information was obtained through a survey. The researcher-made questionnaires were provided in two sets, one for each group of respondents. The questionnaire contained a few demographic and general questions, followed by nine and 13 open-ended questions for students and teachers, respectively. The questions revolve around the students’ writing skills, teachers’ use of authentic assessment in writing, and the perceptions of both in the implementation of the aforementioned assessment.

The locale of the study was at Antipolo National High School, located in Barangay Antipolo, Minalabac, Camarines Sur. The school provided a suitable environment to gather information about writing and authentic assessment. The participants consisted of 45 Grade 10 students and five English teachers and were chosen through a purposive sampling method. The selection of Grade 10 students was due to their grade level and capability to comprehend the questions and relate their writing task experiences based on their four years in junior high school. The expertise of the high school English teachers was requested, as this covered their implementation and perceptions of authentic assessment.

The secondary source of information is the systematic literature review, which was accomplished following the rigorous process of the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) 2020 expanded checklist created by Page et al. (2020). The checklist contains 27 items encompassing introduction, methodology, results, discussion, and other information. The checklist primarily synthesizes information from quantitative references; however, the researcher opted for a qualitative analysis of the collected data.

After the collection of data from primary and secondary sources, they were analyzed using Braun and Clarke’s thematic analysis to capture the essence of qualitative data (Byrne, 2021). This particular analysis facilitates the identification and exploration of patterns or themes in a given dataset. The first stage is the familiarization with the data, which was done after obtaining the surveys, and the researcher encoded the data in the

Word program and reviewed it to grasp a general overview of the respondents' responses. The second stage involved generating initial codes using a qualitative data analysis software called Delve. In the third stage, the codes were renamed, merged, removed, reclassified, and defined to form a broader set of themes. The themes were grouped according to similarities and categories. When the themes were organized, the fifth step required that themes be defined with the codes listed under them. Lastly, the sixth step was the creation of a write-up discussing the themes.

After the first process, the second process was the design of the assessment tool; the design stage was concentrated on specifying the gaps generated in the analysis. Once the gaps were identified through the survey and systematic literature review, the outlining and planning of the assessment tool commenced. This process focused on determining the learning objectives and the gaps and challenges in the study, which served as the basis for drafting the assessment tool. Once the outline was prepared and expanded, an authentic assessment tool was created to improve students' writing competence.

The study was completed in only a year, focusing on determining students' writing abilities, understanding authentic assessment perceptions and implementation, and designing an authentic assessment tool. The study did not cover more input from students and teachers concerning writing and authentic assessment, the systematic literature review did not utilize meta-analysis for more robust statistical responses, and the methodology did not incorporate the implementation and evaluation of the assessment tool in terms of its effectiveness and practicality. The study only underscored the design of an authentic assessment tool for improving students' writing competence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cross-Case Analysis of the Primary and Secondary Data

The analysis stage is accomplished through a two-pronged methodology: an analysis of primary information from survey responses and a breakdown of secondary data from a systematic literature review of related studies and literature. The answers from the questionnaire generated six themes, and the comprehensive literature review rendered three. These themes were then combined in a third analysis, which is the cross-case analysis, where a synthesis matrix was employed to merge identical or parallel data. As summarized in Table 1, the cross-case analysis produced six general themes from the sources that yielded the following, which are the definition and advantages of authentic assessment, challenges and solutions for implementing authentic assessment, and characteristics of authentic assessment, such as designing authentic writing assessment, authentic assessment implementation strategies and tasks, support for the execution of authentic writing assessments, and different authentic assessment evaluation strategies.

Table 1. Synthesis Matrix of all the Sub-Themes from Primary and Secondary Sources

No.	Theme/s	Primary Source	Secondary Source
1	Definition and advantages of authentic assessment	Authentic assessment is an alternative form of assessment Authentic assessment benefits students' overall writing skills	Authentic assessment is a presentation of skills and knowledge that reflects real-world settings Authentic assessment strengthens students' skill development, knowledge acquisition, and workability
2	Challenges and solutions for implementing authentic assessment	Authentic assessment is a challenge to plan and implement Overcoming authentic assessment challenges through a series of planning and considerations	Obstacles in implementing authentic writing assessment Considerations in planning and executing authentic writing assessments
3	Designing of authentic writing assessment/ Characteristics of authentic assessment	Factors in planning authentic writing assessment Convenience and reservations in the use of technology Writing follows a series of processes	The drafting of authentic assessment must be anchored on real-life tasks
4	Authentic assessment implementation strategies and tasks/ Characteristics of authentic assessment	Helpful strategies for doing authentic assessment Writing tasks that students want to do more often	Students play an important role in the conduct of an authentic assessment
5	Support for the execution of authentic writing assessments	Examples of assistance to aid students in improving their authentic writing skills	
6	Different authentic	Evaluation and	Evaluation factors in

assessment evaluation strategies/ Characteristics of authentic assessment	communication of authentic writing assessments	assessing authentic assessment
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The first theme discusses the collective input from the survey questionnaire and literature review about the definition and impacts of authentic assessment. In the primary source, authentic assessment is defined as an alternative form of assessment. This is grounded on the teachers' perceptions that authentic assessment is another method of assessing students' learning that deviates from the traditional pen-paper testing, which translates to authentic assessment aiming to go beyond the traditional methods of assessment. Similarly, the data found in the secondary source defines authentic assessment as a presentation or demonstration of skills and knowledge that reflects real-world settings. The authentic assessment must ensure that application of learning is evident in tasks that have relevance to students' real-life experiences.

In the same theme, impacts and advantages are discussed, and codes were obtained from both the survey questionnaire and the systematic literature review. Based on the primary source, authentic assessment benefits students' overall writing skills, such as that it improves cognitive abilities, develops written and communication skills, and prepares students for the real world. Likewise, it is found in the secondary source that authentic assessment strengthens students' skill development, knowledge acquisition, and workability. The latter are grounded on the codes that improve overall skills and attributes, promote long-term student engagement, and enhance graduate employability.

Students' and teachers' knowledge of authentic assessment is necessary as the education sector mandates that they must adapt to its demands in the volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) 21st century (Bushweller, 2021). VUCA in education relies on skill development as technology has changed and continues to change the playing field of how things are done, which means students must prepare for future undertakings of their preferred profession to secure their success. Authentic assessment is not new in education and assessment, but it has garnered worldwide support and interest from scholars, curriculum designers, and educators. There is a drive to apply authentic assessment in more facets of the curriculum; indeed, authentic assessment has been accepted at different levels in the education sector as an alternative or supplement to traditional assessments.

The second theme features the codes referring to the challenges, considerations, and solutions for implementing authentic assessment. According to the primary source, authentic assessment is a challenge to plan and implement, whereas the secondary source states that there are obstacles in implementing authentic writing assessment. The former source lists implementation challenges like cognitive or language challenges, time management and pressure, writing apprehension, and challenges in diversity, instruction, and tasks. These challenges in implementing and doing authentic assessment were provided by the teacher and students in the survey questionnaire. The latter lists the challenges, such as resource-intensive, challenging, and students' poor linguistic

proficiency.

The implementation of authentic assessment is not without challenges. However, there have been resolutions found from primary and secondary sources that could alleviate the concerns in the implementation of authentic assessment. From the primary source, overcoming authentic assessment challenges can be achieved through a series of planning and considerations, such as instructional planning, pre-writing techniques, time and task management, motivation, and collaborative learning and teamwork. From the secondary source, considerations in planning and executing authentic assessment can be done through contemplation on the education, training, and experience of students and teachers, manageability, and alignment of instruction and assessment.

It is crucial to resolve the concerns regarding the challenges of implementing authentic assessment, specifically in teaching writing. The assessment can help improve the writing competence of the students if they are used to achieve the desired learning competencies.

The third theme combined sub-themes of designing an authentic writing assessment and the characteristics of authentic assessment from primary and secondary sources, respectively. The survey analysis yielded the sub-theme about the factors in planning authentic assessment, the convenience and reservations in the use of technology, and writing follows a series of processes. On the other hand, the literature review generated the context for drafting an authentic assessment. It is important to note that there are factors to be considered when planning an authentic assessment that includes its framework, delivery or demonstration, and level of complexity.

Designing an authentic assessment requires planning and knowledge of its nature. During the design process, it is significant to reflect on the use of performance tasks or assessments that have relevance outside of the classroom. In this way, students are sufficiently prepared to take on the challenges after they complete the course, year, or degree.

The fourth theme merged the sub-themes from both primary and secondary sources with respect to the strategies or techniques that teachers and students need in the execution of an authentic writing assessment. Based on the first source of data, students require helpful strategies for doing authentic assessments, such as real-world tasks and activities, clear writing instruction, collaboration, reflection, and a supportive learning environment. With regards to the tasks that students want to do more often, they highlighted the desire to learn and practice writing essays, personal expressions and reflections, creative writing, and real-world tasks. Moreover, the information found in the secondary source includes the role of the students in the success of the assessment. These roles include a need for defense or demonstration of the tasks, multiple assessments, and collaboration with others.

Students play an important role in the assessment process, since they are the recipients of the assessment, and it is crucial that their input is considered in the planning

and execution of any task. Authenticity relies on what is genuine for the students, and understanding students' experiences will help implementers and educators craft a task that will not only be suitable for the students' level but will also be relevant to their outside-of-the-classroom experiences.

The fifth theme refers to the support that can be provided for the students and teachers in the conduct of an authentic assessment. Performing or accomplishing an authentic assessment is not an easy task, especially for students. For example, when students are not familiar with a specific writing task, it is difficult for them to comply with the submission. For this reason, the student and teacher respondents of the survey expressed their opinions and appealed for assistance. Based on the primary source, students ask for regular writing sessions and workshops to provide remedial exercises for them to hone their writing skills. Additionally, they seek motivation and emotional support in accomplishing tasks and request timely feedback on their submissions. Teachers have also expressed the need for teacher support and professional development in terms of understanding the planning and implementation of authentic assessments.

Teachers and students are at the center of the teaching and learning process, and it is of paramount importance that they are assisted and supported. By providing support to teachers and students in conducting authentic assessments, they are more likely to succeed in achieving the standards and goals set by the educational body.

The sixth theme of data from primary and secondary sources includes the evaluation and communication factors in assessing authentic assessment. The codes from the primary source cover the assessment strategies, transparency of learning standards and progress, and technological feedback. The secondary source provides the codes that scoring criteria must be known or student-centered, there should be multiple indicators for scoring, and the performance standard should manifest mastery. Evaluation is of paramount importance in the conduct of an authentic assessment because it shows how students learn about their progress and how teachers determine the success of the teaching process.

Putting importance on the evaluation stage is crucial as it determines the success of the assessment, and it is the culmination of the efforts of the teachers and students that will decide the effectiveness of the strategies leading to the task. Feedback and evaluation phases are fundamental aspects of learning and assessment; these are the stages where students understand what to improve, and teachers use these as a foundation to base their marks. However, learning does not stop after the evaluation marks have been given and received. Evaluation is only a link from one task to another, and it reveals whether the students are ready for a more challenging task or require a remedial of the learned knowledge.

Design of the Authentic Assessment Tool

The design stage refers to the stage that involves planning the instructional materials. This stage focuses on the output design, such as the learning objectives, selection of strategies, and plan for the output structure. This study's research objective was the foundation for designing an authentic English assessment tool for enhancing writing competence, and gaps were identified to pave the way for the solution of the research objective. Codes about the definition, impacts, and characteristics of authentic assessment were also generated from survey responses and literature review to institute the guide and scope of the authentic assessment tool.

In the design stage, the learning objectives and goals of the assessment tool were anchored from the definition and impacts of authentic assessment, taken from the survey questionnaire and literature review analyses. The codes generated in those two sources would be contextualized to the writing skill, which the assessment tool must strive to attain the objectives and goals of an authentic assessment. Here is the refined outline of the objectives and goals of an authentic assessment:

Assessment objectives:

The authentic assessment must:

1. show a traditional approach to the assessment of writing competence and incorporate a level of authenticity or task fidelity;
2. present a demonstration of acquired writing skills and knowledge, such as writing output or a collection of written tasks in a portfolio; and
3. contain features or qualities of writing tasks relevant to students' real-life goals, tasks, and experiences.

Goals of the authentic writing assessment tool:

1. improve overall writing skills and attributes, such as cognitive and communication skills;
2. promote life-long or long-term student engagement or application of learning; and
3. prepare the students for success in academic, real-world, and workforce.

The design stage has covered an authentic assessment's learning objectives and goals based on the assessment's definition and impacts; the content of the assessment tool was anchored on the characteristics of authentic assessment found from the combined codes of the survey questionnaire and literature review. The specific assessment tool—a rubric—was selected based on the research objective and collected data because a rubric is defined to make explicit a range of assessment criteria and expected performance standards (University of New South Wales – Sydney, 2024). The rubric checks or assesses students' output or performance from a list or grid of standards. The decision to create an authentic assessment tool in a rubric format was partly due to

two reasons: one, the teachers who answered the survey questionnaire needed a rubric, and second, the nature of a rubric is suitable for the research objective.

An authentic assessment tool to improve student writing competence was initially formulated to form a 25-item checklist based on the combined characteristics of the primary and secondary sources of data. However, after the initial deliberation of the assessment tool, it was found that some attributes share similarities. Thus, similarities were merged, and it was improved to a 12-item rubric with four indicators of evidence: very low, low, moderate, and high. The rubric contains three main categories: the context of the authentic writing task, the process of the authentic writing task, and the evaluation of the authentic writing task, where the first category contains five attributes, the second has three, and the last features four attributes. The rubric is illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2. English Authentic Assessment Tool

ENGLISH AUTHENTIC ASSESSMENT TOOL				
General assessment objectives				
The authentic assessment must:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • show a non-traditional approach to assessment of writing competence and incorporate a level of authenticity or task fidelity; • present a demonstration of acquired writing skills and knowledge, such as writing output or a collection of written tasks in a portfolio; and • contain features or qualities of writing tasks that are relevant to students' real-life goals, tasks, and experiences. 				
The authentic assessment aims to:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improve overall writing skills and attributes, such as cognitive and communication skills; • promote life-long or long-term student engagement or application of learning; and • prepare the students for success in academic, real-world, and workforce. 				
No.	Attribute	Indicator	Scale of Evidence	Remarks
Context of the Authentic Writing Task				
1	Fidelity of the authentic writing assessment	Replicate a realistic writing activity or assessment task that manifests real-world application and real-life situations.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High	
		The fidelity of the authentic assessment must be in accordance with how the task is done in the real world.		

2	Alignment of the authentic tasks with assessment methods and instruments	Align the instrument or assessment tool with the assessment tasks. The tool must be a suitable method for evaluating students' writing competence.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High
3	The task is cognitively complex	Plan a task that is one higher level than the students' competence or skill. The task must be challenging to allow for the utilization of higher-order thinking skills but not too difficult that it discourages the students from trying, completing, or undertaking.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High
4	Manageability	<p>Consider the pair or group works for classes with large class sizes. Adopt collaborative groupings.</p> <p>Allot an ample amount of time for the completion of the assessment task, considering how these tasks would normally be completed in the real world.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High
5	Student's writing interests	Reflect on the description of the assessment task with regard to the education level and student's writing interests.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High
Process of the authentic writing task			
6	Planning	Provide before pre-writing activities that allow for generating, organizing, and goal-setting of ideas and task completion.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High
7	Translating	Encourage the students to create outlines, mind maps, thematic maps, spider webs, and other graphic aids to translate ideas into visible language.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High

8	Reviewing	Allot ample strategies and activities for students to evaluate and revise their written work.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High
Evaluation of the authentic writing task			
9	Defense of the output is required	Allot a time or schedule for students to perform or present their work in front of their fellow students or teachers. A brief explanation of their writing process and output is recommended to guarantee the originality and integrity of the submission.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High
10	Application of metacognition	Allow students to reflect on their learning, task completion, and experience. Metacognition could be done through guided reflection or simple journaling of thoughts and experiences.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High
11	The scoring criteria are known or student-developed	Include students in the creation of the scoring criteria to seek their input about the assessment task and to maintain transparency in the evaluation process. The goal is to create an environment of inclusivity and responsibility for their learning.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High
12	Feedback	<p>Provide feedback on the students' assessment tasks, either oral or written.</p> <p>Demonstrate the suggestions if possible.</p> <p>Use technology or AI tools in evaluating the students' work. Examples are a plagiarism checker, writing assistance, and more.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> High

The first group covers the context of the task, specifically the planning of authentic writing assessment, and has five attributes. These attributes are task fidelity, alignment

of authentic tasks and assessment methods, the cognitive challenge of the authentic task, manageability, and students' writing interests.

The first attribute features the fidelity of the authentic writing assessment; fidelity in evaluation refers to the extent to which an intervention is implemented as intended. It provides information on whether the intervention successfully achieved its desired outcome (Ginsburg et al., 2021). The fidelity of assessment referred to in this assessment tool means the imitation or replication of a writing task or assessment task that manifests real-world application and real-life situations; in other words, the writing task must mirror a task that students may often do in the future.

The second attribute is the alignment of the task assessment methods and instruments. The authentic tasks must be aligned with how the students will be assessed, and the methods and instruments must show the standards or competencies students need to achieve. If the real-world task is evaluated in a certain way, the students' authentic writing tasks must show at least an overview of the same assessment style. In this way, students will be informed about how their writing outputs will be assessed, and they can carry out the assessment tool even after completing the grade level or program.

The third attribute requires that tasks must be cognitively complex, as evidenced by one of the English teachers' concerns was that some students could not do the writing tasks for various reasons, so they strive to lower the standards so that students can meet them. Such action is a student-friendly intervention to ensure that everyone can do the task and finish the grade level or graduate from the program; however, this also threatens students' competence because they will not be on par with the curriculum standards and their peers from other schools. Therefore, the tasks must be designed and implemented uniformly and should be cognitively complex to challenge students' competencies. The challenge will bring out their higher-level thinking skills, but it is necessary to note that the level of complexity must be within the students' skills to avoid triggering disinterest, anxiety, or overall writing apprehension.

The fourth attribute refers to the manageability of the tasks because authentic assessments are innovative ways to provide students with meaningful assessment situations. On the other hand, the design and implementation of such can be exhausting for the students; certain situations cannot accommodate authentic assessments in the classroom due to a lack of resources, time, or other important factors. In this situation, the students are still given an authentic assessment experience, but some factors will be changed for manageability.

The fifth attribute includes students' writing interests, as these could be employed as inspiration or a springboard for the authentic writing task; their inclusion should be considered in the implementation of the assessment. When students relate to the writing tasks, their experience might make the activity more interesting and appealing. On that note, the writing task should also consider the education level of the student, and it is significant to remember that authenticity in all assessments is difficult to achieve. If the writing task resembles some authenticity, it can be considered authentic; authenticity must be defined according to the student's level. An authentic writing task for a grade one

pupil differs from that of a grade ten student.

To sum up, the use of five different attributes to form the context of the task is essential. It covers the task, how the task is handled, and the considerations for the design of the task. These attributes will be helpful for teachers in designing and implementing authentic tasks, making sure that all necessary variables or factors are included. It is also important to note that authenticity is a spectrum. There is no one way to attest to the authenticity of a task. Authenticity must also depend on what is authentic or “real” for the students.

These attributes contribute to what authentic assessment is. Based on the constructivist learning theory by Jean Piaget, learning must promote active learning with hands-on application. When students are treated as active learners instead of passive ones, there will be better and longer-term memory retention. Additionally, the situated learning theory by Brown et al. supports the context of the authentic task. Based on the second theory, there must be interaction between the learner and the environment. The learning will be much more successful if the students are provided with learning tasks relevant to their experiences and needs.

The second group of attributes in the rubric refers to authentic writing tasks anchored on Flower and Hayes’s cognitive process theory of writing. The attributes are planning, translating, and reviewing.

The sixth overall attribute refers to planning. In the planning stage, the students must be given pre-writing activities to activate their schema or background knowledge. These activities include generating ideas, organizing ideas, and setting goals to be achieved by the end of the writing assessment. It is essential that planning is given ample time to allow students to research and brainstorm.

The seventh overall attribute refers to translating. The translating stage covers the creation of outlines, mind maps, thematic maps, spider webs, and other graphic aids to help the students convert abstract ideas into visible language. The writing stage is a beneficial activity that allows students to filter essential ideas from non-essential ones. Translating is also the stage where they use the outlines to write sentences, paragraphs, and papers, and the stage when they convert ideas to written words in the paper.

The eighth attribute refers to reviewing. The reviewing stage must include ample strategies and activities for students to evaluate and revise their written work. The reviewing stage is where they check their paper's content, organization, voice, grammar, and mechanics. Reviewing can be done individually, in pairs, or with the help of a more knowledgeable other. Students often disregard reviewing as they consider submitting a created output the last step, and leave the editing, reviewing, and revising to their teachers. Students must be involved in the review of their work so they can work on improving any errors in their writing.

The sixth, seventh, and eighth attributes constitute the second group of the rubric. The current study deviated from most writing instructions' typical pre-writing, during-

writing, and post-writing stages. It is due to a particular factor needed in the writing process—monitoring. The monitoring happens in all stages because the proponents believe that writing is not simply a linear process but a hierarchical one. They claim that the writing process happens when students go back and forth in their writing, checking their ideas, writing, and other factors. These stages are crucial in the writing process so that students are guided.

These processes are anchored on the cognitive process theory of writing by Linda Flower and John Hayes. The theory stipulates that writing happens through the major components, such as planning, translating/drafting, and revising/editing. The theory emphasizes monitoring throughout the writing process to guarantee success. It also explains that writing is not a linear process but a hierarchical one.

The last group of rubric attributes conveys the evaluation strategies of authentic writing tasks. These strategies include defending the output, applying metacognition, using student-developed or known scoring criteria, and providing feedback.

The ninth attribute refers to the defense of the output. Writing is a different skill compared to other macro-skills, and because of its complicated nature, some students are enticed to easily copy ideas and outputs online and present them as their own. In order to alleviate such concerns, the students must defend their work either by presenting it to the class or by checking with a teacher. The process of presenting a defense or evidence of their work assures that the originality and integrity of the submission are checked.

The tenth attribute is the application of metacognition. Metacognition is the awareness and understanding of one's thought processes, and it is helpful because students become aware of their learning and how they process it. When students are encouraged to assess their thinking, they are more able to reflect on their knowledge and its relevance to their lives. The process of metacognition could be done through guided reflection or journaling of thoughts and experiences.

The eleventh attribute refers to the scoring criteria. These criteria must be known or communicated, and developed by the students. Students are included in creating the assessment criteria to inform them of the required standards. Also, by including students in making the requirements, the students can provide input on the difficulty and achievability of the standards. Communicating the assessment criteria to the students promotes transparency and inclusivity among the students and teachers.

The twelfth attribute is feedback; this pertains to providing input to the students that is essential in their development of the skill. The feedback can be formative and summative. The teachers can opt to provide feedback on the students' assessment tasks, either oral or written. Demonstration of suggestions is also suggested so the students can understand how to improve their work. The use of technology or AI tools in evaluating students' work can also be considered, provided that the teacher has checked the veracity of the feedback from the tools.

Students appreciate when their teachers provide input regarding their work. Often, they prefer a more positive critique of their outputs and are less inclined to receive negative comments. However, constructive criticism is necessary to improve the work and the student. When students are enlightened about why they get certain marks, they understand the value of their work. They are informed of the suggestions to improve their future outputs, and the writing errors will be reduced.

Feedback is supported by situated learning theory by Brown et al., which instructs that learning is not the outcome of the individual mind but emerges from the interaction of the individual with their people and environment, and is a two-way process involving both the teachers and the students. In this case, the interaction between the teacher and students can encourage improvement and learning.

The inclusion of a rubric is supported by the study of Nguyen and Phan (2020), which discusses the advantages of using authentic assessment. The study advocates the utilization of authentic assessment as it assists in reaching the goals of education practices through the authenticity of equity and innovation. In writing, students can improve their proficiency by crafting tasks that are avenues for skill development and preparation for future endeavors.

Another study by Villarroel et al. (2018) emphasizes the advantage of a rubric in using authentic assessment to promote learning. Authentic assessment replicates the tasks and performance standards, and the study created a blueprint for implementing the assessment. The dimensions found in the study are used to propose a step-based model for designing and operating authentic assessments. The intention of the aforementioned study is comparable to the current study by designing an assessment tool to enhance writing competence.

The abovementioned and current studies reveal that authentic assessment effectively enhances students' writing competence. Moreover, the rubric implies that it will influence educators in planning, designing, conducting, and evaluating authentic assessment tasks. The employment of a rubric ensures that necessary particulars are considered in the task's implementation. It thereby merits advantages for students as they will receive assessment tasks that follow their learning standards, and the curriculum will likewise improve because of the enhanced approach to assessment of students' learning.

Conclusions

The rubric has three main categories or groups: the context of the authentic writing task, the process of the authentic writing task, and the evaluation of the authentic writing task. These groups are the general areas teachers must consider when designing and implementing authentic writing assessments. The first group, which entails the context of the writing task, contains five attributes: fidelity of the authentic writing assessment, alignment of the authentic tasks and assessment methods and instruments, the task must be cognitively complex, manageability, and the student's writing interests. The second group refers to the process of authentic writing tasks and has three processes, which are planning, translating, and reviewing. The last group covers the evaluation of the authentic

writing task, such as the defense of the required output, application of metacognition, the scoring guide known or student-developed, and feedback.

The significant feature of the designed assessment tool is the culmination or inclusion of the twelve attributes to form a rubric; based on the definition of the research objective, the assessment tool refers to an instrument used for assessing students' outputs or performances. A rubric is an assessment tool widely used in assessments or evaluations, and the ideas or contents from the rubric were generated from the survey and systematic literature review conducted by the researcher. The researcher created the indicators or descriptions for each attribute to match the writing competence requirements. The evidence scale was added to attest to the implementation of a particular attribute; the scale of evidence ranges from very low, low, moderate, and high. The last column, remarks, was added so the teachers could write their input regarding a particular attribute's feasibility, success, or challenges.

Recommendations

The recommendations include implementing and evaluating the rubric. The first step is to evaluate the rubric's validity, reliability, and practicality; the evaluation can be done with the help of at least three expert validators to assess the effectiveness and trustworthiness of the assessment tool. Recommendations from the expert validators would be used to improve the rubric, and once approved, the implementation stage will be done. The implementation can be done at any grade level, particularly in junior high school, with writing competencies embedded in its curriculum. After the implementation stage, a secondary evaluation would assess whether the rubric has improved students' writing competence. Moreover, continuous study must be done to examine the impacts of authentic assessment in enhancing students' writing competence.

To conclude, designing and implementing an authentic assessment tool is a rigorous process that requires time, preparation, resources, and careful planning from teachers and students. It is time-consuming and resource-intensive, and could strain the faculty and add an unnecessary burden on students' academic workload. The rubric's goal is to provide a straightforward assessment tool to teachers using authentic assessment as an alternative method of evaluating students' writing competence.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Scientific research is essential in furthering knowledge and adding to the existing body of knowledge to help understand the current conditions and prevailing practices. However, to respect the privacy of the respondents, following the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher will not publicize the names of the respondents; each student and teacher was assigned a code to keep their names private and facilitate unbiased analysis of their responses.

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